

THE FIGHT AGAINST CORRUPTION: A VITAL FACTOR IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE STATE AND SOCIETY

Jo'rayev Muhiddin O'tkirovich

Responsible Officer of the Ministry of Internal
Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan,

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Law

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Abstract: This article analyzes the negative impact of corruption on the development of society and the state, as well as the organizational and legal framework for its prevention and combat. The author substantiates that the fight against corruption is not merely the task of law enforcement agencies but a strategic process that requires broad public participation. The article also highlights international experience in this field and the priority areas of Uzbekistan's anti-corruption policy.

Keywords: corruption, public administration, societal development, legal consciousness, openness, transparency, reform, conflict of interest.

Undoubtedly, one of the most dangerous threats facing the global community today is corruption. It not only erodes the economic foundations of the state but also leads to the violation of social justice principles and a decline in citizens' trust in public administration. The scourge of corruption has permeated all spheres of public life, serving as a serious impediment to democratic reforms and sustainable development.

In the reform strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in recent years, the fight against corruption has been designated as one of the priority areas of state policy. Indeed, as our President has emphasized, "In the fight against corruption, not only law enforcement agencies but the entire society must unite." This necessitates a comprehensive study of the issue from legal, institutional, and educational perspectives.

The relevance of this article lies in the fact that the anti-corruption process is not limited to applying punitive measures; it is directly linked to systemic prevention, ensuring transparency in public service, and fostering an intolerant attitude (immunity) towards corruption within society. Within the scope of this article, modern mechanisms for eradicating corruption, the role of digital technologies in this area, and matters of improving national legislation are scientifically analyzed.

Within the priority area of further reforming the judicial and legal system in our state, important tasks have been set for improving the organizational and legal mechanisms for combating corruption and for increasing the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures, namely:

Firstly, elevating the fight against corruption to a new level, both qualitatively and quantitatively, is a product of the political will of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In particular, it is no exaggeration to say that special attention is being paid to the Head of State's ideas on the necessity of "inoculating society with the 'honesty vaccine'."

As the President noted in his Address to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 24, 2020, "The evil of corruption in our society, with its various manifestations, is hindering our development. If we do not prevent this scourge, it will be impossible to create a genuine business and investment climate, and no sector of society will develop at all."

Secondly, measures are being taken to systematically improve the regulatory and legal framework in the field. As proof of our opinion, we can cite the entry into force of the law on combating corruption, as well as the adoption of various bylaws. For example, on January 3, 2017, the President of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, signed the Law "On Combating Corruption." The purpose of this Law is to regulate relations in the field of anti-corruption, which, along with clarifying such basic concepts as "corruption," "corruption offense," "conflict of interest," also outlines the basic principles of anti-corruption. The law also enshrines the main directions of state policy in the field of combating corruption, the system of authorized bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, civil society institutions, the mass media, and citizen participation in this field, measures to prevent corruption, ensuring the inevitability of punishment, and international cooperation in this field.

Third, a special state body has been established for the effective implementation of measures, and the institutional foundations of state policy in this area have been improved. For example, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. In accordance with the Decree, the Anti-Corruption Agency was established to form and implement state policy in the field of preventing and combating corruption, as well as state and other programs aimed at eliminating the systemic causes and conditions of corruption offenses and increasing the effectiveness of anti-corruption measures. Foreign experience was thoroughly studied, promoting international norms in defining the legal foundations, tasks, functions, rights, and obligations of the Agency's activities. Its most favorable aspects are fully reflected in this Presidential Decree. One of the main tasks of the agency is to develop international cooperation in the field of preventing and combating corruption, as well as to implement systemic measures to strengthen the country's image and enhance its position in international rankings. The National Anti-Corruption Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan and its regional councils have been established. The primary objective of these reforms is to eradicate the vices of corruption.

Fourthly, state programs are being adopted, covering all state and public organizations and measures to be implemented at the national level. For example, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 2, 2017, the first State Program for Combating Corruption for 2017–2018 was adopted, and specific measures were implemented within its framework. Continuing these reforms,

On May 27, 2019, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the anti-corruption system in the Republic of Uzbekistan" approved the next State Anti-Corruption Program for 2019-2020. One of the latest steps in this direction is the State Anti-Corruption Program for 2021-2022, approved by the Presidential Decree "On measures to create an environment of zero tolerance for corruption, drastically reduce corruption factors in state and public administration, and expand public participation in this process" dated July 6, 2021. It outlines 44 measures with specific deadlines, responsible executors, and implementation mechanisms.

Fifth, ensuring the openness and transparency of the activities of state bodies based on anti-corruption measures is defined as a priority task in the country. For example, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On additional measures to ensure the openness of the activities of state bodies and organizations, as well as the effective implementation of public control" dated June 16, 2021, it was introduced that all state

authorities and administration bodies, including the Accounts Chamber, the Central Bank, judicial and prosecutorial bodies and their structural and territorial divisions, as well as business entities with a state share in the authorized fund (authorized capital) of 50 percent or more and state unitary enterprises, must approve a list of socially significant information to be posted as open data. Additionally, the "Openbudget" portal was launched to exercise public control over the regulation of budget expenditures, notify citizens of violations of budget legislation, and organize the procedure for submitting proposals to improve the budget process.

Sixthly, another important aspect of the fight against corruption is the optimization of state bodies and the enhancement of their efficiency, which are being implemented systematically and in stages. For example, on April 3, 2021, the President signed a resolution on reducing the number of staff units of state authorities and administration. In accordance with the resolution, the number of employees of state bodies has been optimized up to 15 percent. As a result, a total of 5,288 staff positions were reduced in state authorities and administration bodies, as well as in their departmental and territorial divisions. Additionally, the positions of 40 deputy heads of ministries and departments have been reduced.

Seventh, one of the most important aspects of preventing and eliminating corruption is the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies into state and public administration to reduce the "human factor" in the public administration system. In order to eliminate administrative and bureaucratic barriers, simplify and increase the speed of registration, licensing, and permitting procedures, 201 public service centers have been established in all regions.

Eighth, the fight against corruption is carried out in conjunction with the implementation of international experience and relevant legal norms into the country's legislation and practice. For example, the creation of the Anti-Corruption Agency can serve as an example of the implementation in the country of the relevant articles of the UN Convention against Corruption, ratified by Uzbekistan, as well as the "Jakarta Principles" in international anti-corruption practice.

Ninth, the creation of an uncompromising anti-corruption environment is carried out with the broad participation of the public. For example, the system for reviewing appeals from individuals and legal entities has been radically improved; the People's and Virtual Receptions of the President, the "helpline," and the "helplines" and "virtual receptions" of every ministry and state agency have been established, and the practice of holding "mobile receptions" by heads of state at all levels has been established to ensure the rights and freedoms of citizens.

Tenth, the widespread implementation of a "compliance control" system in government bodies and business entities is underway as part of the fight against corruption. For example, the 2019–2020 State Anti-Corruption Program put forward relevant tasks for introducing an anti-corruption "compliance control" system in organizations with a state share in their authorized capital, monitoring its effectiveness, and establishing a certification procedure in accordance with the relevant anti-corruption standard (ISO 37001). Based on these designated tasks, the Anti-Corruption Agency is working to reduce the share of the shadow economy and implement an internal anti-corruption "compliance control" system in 26 ministries and agencies.

The following can be cited as the main factors behind the positive results in the fight against corruption:

- The prioritization of applying preventive mechanisms and the establishment of the Agency;
- The signing of decrees and resolutions by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan that define specific measures for preventing and combating corruption;
- The digitalization of public procurement processes and the creation of a system for conducting them through online platforms;
- The improvement of licensing and permitting procedures to radically enhance the business and investment climate;
- Increased transparency in the licensing process.

Over the past two years, Uzbekistan has demonstrated significant positive indicators in the fight against corruption within the Central Asian region. This, in turn, is evidence that the reforms being carried out in the country's anti-corruption sphere are yielding effective results

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